

Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period

By Bernhard Schneider, University of Innsbruck

Entry tags: Religious Group, Mesopotamian Religions, Sumerian Religions, Middle Bronze Age, Near East

Nippur was the unrivaled religious capital during the period dominated by the kings of the IIIrd dynasty centered at Ur in nowadays southern Iraq. As the city of the supreme god Enlil it can be considered as the "Mesopotamian Vatican" latest since the Akkad period (c. 2350 BC). The centrality of Nippur at the border between Akkad (North) and Sumer (South) might have triggered the factor of importance of the site. During Ur III times large scale construction programs at the East-mound of the site with the temple of Enlil as well as that of Inanna underlines the importance of Nippur during this period. As Ur III period is considered as a kind of "Sumerian renaissance" it was important for the state ideology to venerate the Old Sumerian gods. Probably building on an ancient custom, the kings of Ur were crowned to be kings of Sumer and Akkad at Nippur. Reconstructed with the help of the Puzrish-Dagan (modern Drehem) texts which were excavated illegally at a site nearby Nippur, the ritual calendar can be reconstructed. Each month a festival was celebrated which was often related to a specific god as, for example, the *gu4-si-su* (sum.) festival of the second month (c. April/May) which was dedicated to Enlil's son Ninurta who was also known as, *lugal gu4-si-su* (sum.), "king of the Gusu". One of the most important local religious celebrations was the festival at the nearby site of Tummal (modern Dlehim) with a boat procession to the ancient cultic center of Enlil's wife Ninlil. Additionally, festivals related to agriculture like the seeding (fourth month, sum. *shu-numun*) were also common. Other important gods at Nippur were the healing goddess Gula/Ninisina in the local form of Nintinuga (sum. "Lady who revives the dead"). Her temple was probably localized by excavations at the northern West-mound.

Date Range: 2100 BCE - 2000 BCE

Region: Ur III core region

Region tags: Southern Iraq, Al-Qadisiyah, Southern Mesopotamia

Core region of the Ur III kingdom roughly between 2100 and 2000 BC.

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Sallaberger, Walther. *Der kultische Kalender der Ur III-Zeit. Untersuchungen zur Assyriologie und Vorderasiatischen Archäologie, Bd. 7.* Berlin: Walter de Gruyter, 1993.
- Source 2: Sallaberger, Walther. *Ur III-Zeit.* In: Walter Sallaberger - Aage Westenholz, *Mesopotamien - Akkade-Zeit und Ur III Zeit.* Orbis Biblicus et Orientalis 160/3. Universitätsverlag Freiburg Schweiz - Vandenhoeck & Ruprecht Göttingen, 1999.
- Source 3: Jacobsen, Thorkild. *The Treasures of Darkness: A History of Mesopotamian Religion.* Yale University Press, 1976.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

- Source 1: Wang, Xianhua. *The Metamorphosis of Enlil*. *Alter Orient und Altes Testament*. Ugarit Verlag, Münster, 2011.
- Source 2: Schneider, Bernhard. *The Materiality of the Foundation of the Ur III Ekur at Nippur*. In: Robert Rollinger, Irene Madreiter, Martin Lang, Cinzia Pappi (eds.), *The Intellectual Heritage of the Ancient Near East Proceedings of the 64th Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale and the 12th Melammu Symposium*, University of Innsbruck, July 16-20, 2018. Pp. 881-892.

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.livius.org/articles/place/nippur/>
- Source 1 Description: Overview of Nippur at Livius.org.
- Source 2 URL: https://cdli.ox.ac.uk/wiki/doku.php?id=year_names
- Source 2 Description: Collection of year names
- Source 3 URL: <http://memare.uksw.edu.pl/>
- Source 3 Description: Mesopotamian Material Religion

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Relevant online primary textual corpora (original languages and/or translations):

- Source 2 URL: <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/>
- Source 2 Description: The ETCSL project, Faculty of Oriental Studies, University of Oxford

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

- Source 1 URL: https://cdli.ucla.edu/search/search_results.php?SearchMode=Text&order=PrimaryPublication&Collection=pennsylvania+museum&Period=ur+iii
- Source 1 Description: Corpus of digitized cuneiform documents. Selected period: Ur III.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religion have official political support

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Is religious infrastructure paid for by the polity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Are political officials equivalent to religious officials:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Is religious observance enforced by the polity:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Polity legal code is roughly coterminous with religious code:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Polity provides preferential economic treatment (e.g. tax, exemption)

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Is there a story (or a set of stories) associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Inspired by high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– Yes

Notes: Originally Enmerkar was a human king but he was deified during Ur III times.

Reference: Robson, Black Zólyomi. "Enmerkar and the Lord of Aratta: Translation". The ETCSL project, Faculty of Oriental Studies, University of Oxford, n.d..

<https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/section1/tr1823.htm>.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Notes: Originally Enmerkar was a human king but he was deified during Ur III times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Notes: Ziggurats, temples on terraces, highly walled temple precincts.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 13750

Notes: Excavated parts of the main court including the incompletely excavated part of a forecourt to the Southeast.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Tombs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Notes: As most discovered burials of the period were intramural it seems that there was no need for cemeteries. Although, it cannot be excluded that in future cemeteries of the period would be discovered.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Altars:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Devotional markers:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Ziqqurrats as special but not obligatory features of a main temple

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– Only religious public space

– Some public spaces

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Notes: Glyptic iconography shows most of the further elaborated beings and symbols.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Eyes (stylized or not):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Other features of iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

Notes: For example Tummal, cult site of Ninlil, was the goal of yearly processions from Nippur and there is also located the ki-a-nag place of Urnamma, the founder of the Ur III dynasty.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are pilgrimages present:

– Yes

Notes: Tummal, the cult site of Ninlil, was the goal of yearly processions from Nippur

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Interment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Animal co-sacrifices present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are grave goods present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Personal effects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Some wealth (some valuable or useful objects interred):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Other grave goods:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Other formal burial type:

– Yes [specify]: Ki-a-nag, commemoration place for kings as for example Urnammas at Tummal.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Notes: The monarch is on power by the will of Enlil and therefore also crowned first at Nippur then at Ur.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– No

Notes: Enlil was deciding the "great deluge" in the gods assembly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– Yes [specify]: Leader of the gods assembly.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Other form of communication with living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ These supernatural beings can be seen:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ These supernatural beings can be physically felt:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have other knowledge of this world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Non-human supernatural beings have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ These supernatural beings have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ These supernatural beings exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ These supernatural beings possess hunger:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ These supernatural beings possess/exhibit some other feature:

– I don't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Does the religious group possess a variety of supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Organized by kinship based on a family model:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Organized hierarchically:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Is the cause or agent of supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Done only by high god:

– Yes

Notes: Enlil decides over the deluge as the fate of humanity within the divine assembly of the Ekur.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Is the reason for supernatural punishment known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Done to inhibit selfishness:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Other [specify]

– Yes

Notes: To shut up the noise of people the deluge is brought over the world by Enlil.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Is the cause/purpose of supernatural rewards known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

↳ Done only by high god:

– No

↳ Done by many supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Notes: It is generally suggested that the naditu (Akk.)/ lukur (sum.) priestesses were expected to be sexually abstinent or at least to get no children. Although definite proofs only exist for the following Old Babylonian period.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Monogamy (males):

– Yes

Notes: According to the Codex-Urnamma a penalty is due to be payed by a man violating the marriage of another man.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Monogamy (females):

– Yes

Notes: Following the Codex-Urnamma it was expected that married woman would get punished for adultery. Even only an accusation by the husband would lead to a river ordeal of the wife.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Other sexual constraints (males):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Other sexual constraints (females):

– Yes

Notes: It is generally suggested that the naditu (Akk.) priestesses were expected to be sexually abstinent or at least to get no children.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to small-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

I.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale "ceremonies" and "festivals."

– No

Notes: There is no information that it was obligatory to participate in both "ceremonies" and "festivals".

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Tattoos/scarification:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Circumcision:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Hair:

– Yes

Notes: Priests were shaved for ritual cleaning.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Archaic ritual language:

– Yes

Notes: Emesal can be seen as a ritual dialect which was mainly limited to ceremonies in Ur III times.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Notes: Most probably poorer people can give children to temples which is sometimes indicated in the personal name of the individual.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– Yes

Notes: Only elites had access to formal education. The temple as a place of learning is not proven but finds of stray inscriptions from the Ekur temple could lead to such a conclusion.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherents interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– Yes

Notes: Known sources provide evidence for a "magnificent/great boat" (Sum. má-gur8 maḥ) of the divine couple Enlil and Ninlil (see for example preserved in year names of king Shu-suen: [https://cdli.ox.ac.uk/wiki/doku.php?id=year_names_shu-suen: year 8b, 9a](https://cdli.ox.ac.uk/wiki/doku.php?id=year_names_shu-suen:year_8b_9a)). It probably was used as a mode of transport, for example, during a boat procession.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The existence of the "Lawcode of Urnamma" could suggest an independent judicial system.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– Yes

Notes: "Lawcode of Urnamma" could be seen as a formal legal code or at least as a precursor of such a code.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question have the power to conscript:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question maintain a full-time military corps (e.g. Swiss Guard):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Does the religious group in question maintain a standing army:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Notes: With Emesal it possesses only a distinct dialect of Sumerian.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an

institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– Yes

Notes: The Nippur Calendar is mainly connected to the local cult. See Cultic Calendar as reconstructed by Sallaberger 1993.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Notes: The Drehem calendar exists beside the Nippur calendar.

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Please characterize the forms/level of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Fishing

– Pastoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Gathering

– Hunting (including marine animals)

– Fishing

– Patoralism

– Small-scale agriculture / horticultural gardens or orchards

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Region: Ur III core

Bibliography

General References

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Sallaberger, Walther. *Der Kultische Kalender Der Ur Iii-zeit*. Berlin, New York: De Gruyter, 1993. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110889253>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Sallaberger, Walther, and Aage Westenholz. "Mesopotamien: Akkade-zeit Und Ur Iii-zeit. *Orbis Biblicus Et Orientalis*, Vol. 160.3" 120, no. 4 (October 2000). <https://doi.org/10.2307/606649>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Zettler, Richard L., and Walther Sallaberger. "Inana's Festival at Nippur Under the Third Dynasty of Ur". *Zeitschrift Für Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatische Archäologie* 101, no. 1 (January 2011): 1-71. <https://doi.org/10.1515/za.2011.001>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Sallaberger, Walther. "Eine Reiche Bestattung Im Neusumerischen Ur". *Journal of Cuneiform Studies* 47, no. 1 (January 1995): 15-21. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1359811>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Steinkeller, Piotr. "Care for the Elderly in Ur III Times: Some New Insights". *Zeitschrift Für Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatische Archäologie* 108, no. 2 (November 27, 2018): 136-42. <https://doi.org/10.1515/za-2018-0009>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Tsouparopoulou, Christina. "The Healing Goddess, Her

Dogs and Physicians in Late Third Millennium BC Mesopotamia". *Zeitschrift Für Assyriologie Und Vorderasiatische Archäologie* 110, no. 1 (June 25, 2020): 14–24. <https://doi.org/10.1515/za-2020-0002>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Balke, Thomas E., and Christina Tsouparopoulou, eds.. *Materiality of Writing in Early Mesopotamia*. Edited by Thomas E. Balke and Christina Tsouparopoulou. Berlin, Boston: De Gruyter, 2016. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110459630>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Frayne, Douglas. *Ur III Period (2112-2004 BC)*. Toronto: University of Toronto Press, 1997. <https://doi.org/10.3138/9781442657069>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Fish, T.. "The Sumerian City Nippur in the Period of the Third Dynasty of Ur" 5 (1938). <https://doi.org/10.2307/4241631>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, McCown, Donald E.. "Excavations at Nippur, 1948-50". *Journal of Near Eastern Studies* 11, no. 3 (July 1952): 169–76. <https://doi.org/10.1086/371085>.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Schneider, Bernhard. "'nippur: City of Enlil and Ninurta". In C. Bonnet, T. Galoppin, E. Guillon, M. Luaces, A. Lätzer-lasar, S. Lebreton, F. Porzia, J. Rüpke and E. Rubens Urciuoli (eds.), *Naming and Mapping the Gods in the Ancient Mediterranean: Spaces, Mobilities, Imaginaries*. Berlin/boston. Pp. 745-762. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110798432-039>. Berlin/Boston: De Gruyter, 2022.

Reference: Religion at Nippur in the Ur III period, Schneider, Bernhard. "'the Materiality of the Foundation of the Ur III Ekur at Nippur", in R. Rollinger, M. Lang, S. Fink, C. Pappi, I. Madreiter (eds.), *Proceedings of the 64th Rencontre Assyriologique Internationale / 12th Melammu- Symposium, (CRRAI 64), Vienna.*". Vienna: Austrian Academy of Sciences Press, 2023.

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Yes, Robson, Black Zólyomi. "Enmerkar and the Lord of Aratta: Translation". The ETCSL project, Faculty of Oriental Studies, University of Oxford, n.d.. <https://etcsl.orinst.ox.ac.uk/section1/tr1823.htm>.